

Open Science NL

Open Research Software Advisory Panel

Meeting Notes

22 May 2025, 15:00 - 17.00 CEST (UTC + 1:00)

Location: MS Teams

Attendees

- Ana Martinovici
- Daniel S. Katz
- Daniela Gawehns
- John Swinbank
- Martine de Vos
- Morane Gruenpeter (left at 15.50 hrs)
- Santosh Ilamparuthi
- Thomas Pronk
- Mark van Assem - Acting Co-Chair
- Marta Teperek - Acting Chair

Apologies:

- Laurents Sesink
- Mateusz Kuzak
- Vincent Traag
- Maria Cruz, Chair

Absent:

- Karthik Ram

Notes:

Welcome and agenda

The meeting started at 15.02. The panel was informed that minutes of the last meeting have been published on Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/records/14592058>

Netherlands eScience Center update

Marta Teperek gave a confidential update about the situation at the Netherlands eScience Center.

Work Programme 2024 and 2025: implementation update

The panel was updated on the most relevant progress in the implementation of the OSNL Work Programme 2024 – 2025. Namely:

- [Three new digital competence centres have been funded](#): one at the Open University, one joint competence centre for the four philosophical/theological institutions, and a joint digital competence network for the Caribbean region.

- The Open Science Infrastructure call is in progress and it is expected to conclude at the end of 2025.
- The call for proposals “[Research on open science](#)” is now open for submissions. The deadline for proposals is 16 September, 14:00 CEST.
- The next steps with regards to the implementation of the “Research Software Sustainability Programme” are still being discussed.

Development of a Work Programme 2026 and 2027

The discussion about the content of the new Open Science NL Work Programme 2026 and 2027 was confidential and minutes were not taken.

When discussing issues and ideas for a potential Open Science Infrastructure call in the new work programme, the so-called “Metaproject” was mentioned: *van der Graaf, M. (2025). Ontwikkeling van het Strategisch Plan Integrale Infrastructuur voor Open Science (operationeel projectplan). Zenodo.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15387884>. The aim of this project is to perform a comprehensive gap analysis of the open science infrastructure landscape and the specific needs across the Dutch research community. Panel members present in the meeting had not previously heard about the project and some expressed interest in being consulted about the project. MT and MvA advised panel members to reach out to members of the advisory group (listed on page 6 of the document) with potential feedback.

The timeline for the development of the new Work Programme was noted:

What?	When
Community consultations	Q4 2024 (see the report)
Consultations with advisory panels	Q4 2024
First list of ideas discussed with the OSNL Steering Board	April 2025
Second consultation on the ideas with the OSNL Steering Board	May 2025
Consultation on the ideas with the advisory panels	Q2 2025
OSNL office turning the ideas into a work programme draft	Summer 2025
Consultation on the first work programme draft with the OSNL Steering Board	September 2025
Consultation on the work programme draft with the OSNL covenant partners	October 2025
Final discussion and approval of the work programme by the OSNL Steering Board	November 2025
Discussion on the work programme with the advisory panels	November/December 2025
Publishing of the work programme	December 2025

It was noted that it will be helpful to plan another, additional consultation with the advisory panels after the summer, so that the panels could provide feedback on the work programme draft. An extraordinary meeting will be planned for those willing and interested in providing feedback on the work programme.

Meeting close and plans for the upcoming meeting

MT closed the meeting at 17.00 and thanked all panel members for their contributions.